

DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATIC VENTILATION SYSTEM FOR SMART GREENHOUSES

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Annotation: Any agricultural crop requires certain conditions for growth, ripening and fruiting. Temperature, humidity of air and soil play an important role in this. To ensure a constant temperature range in the greenhouse, a ventilation system will be provided, which is designed to create favorable conditions by stabilizing temperature and humidity - the necessary conditions for growing greenhouse plants.

Key words: Temperature, Greenhouse, stabilizing temperature, humidity, electronic sensors, wireless network.

Аннотация: Любая сельскохозяйственная культура требует определенных условий для роста, созревания и плодоношения. Важную роль в этом играют температура, влажность воздуха и почвы. Для обеспечения постоянного температурного режима в теплице будет предусмотрена система вентиляции, которая предназначена для создания благоприятных условий путем стабилизации температуры и влажности - необходимых условий для выращивания тепличных растений.

Ключевые слова: Температура, теплица, стабилизация температуры, влажность, электронные датчики, беспроводная сеть.

Annotatsiya: Har qanday qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlari o'sishi, pishishi va meva berishi uchun ma'lum shart-sharoitlarni talab qiladi. Bunda harorat, havo va tuproq namligi muhim rol o'ynaydi. Issiqxonada doimiy harorat oralg'ini ta'minlash uchun harorat va namlikni barqarorlashtirish orqali qulay sharoitlarni yaratishga mo'ljallangan shamollatish tizimi ta'minlanadi - issiqxona o'simliklarini yetishtirish uchun zarur shart-sharoitlar yaratish zarur.

Kalit so'zlar: Harorat, issiqxona, barqarorlashtiruvchi harorat, namlik, elektron sensorlar, simsiz tarmoq.

Any agricultural crop requires certain conditions for growth, ripening and fruiting. Temperature, humidity of air and soil play an important role in this. To ensure a constant temperature range in the greenhouse, a ventilation system will be provided, which is designed to create favorable conditions by stabilizing temperature and humidity - the necessary conditions for growing greenhouse

plants. Greenhouse ventilation devices will prevent drafts that can destroy plants and future crops. Fresh air entering the greenhouse will be favorable for plants. The system of ventilation of greenhouses will not allow the temperature to rise or fall sharply, which often happens with independent ventilation. With such sharp temperature changes, it will be difficult for plants to grow and bear fruit. Expensive ventilation systems, equipped with various electronic sensors, are able to clearly determine the temperature and humidity in the greenhouse, and immediately respond to changes by opening or closing the window or door.

Such a “smart” system of greenhouses will prevent not only hypothermia or overheating of plants, but also by maintaining the correct temperature, and prevent the development of fungi and harmful microorganisms that adore high humidity and stagnant hot air. You can also set the operating mode so that there is a favorable microclimate for your crops.

By the method of opening the ventilation system can be divided into 3 groups.

The first group - hydraulic systems, including a simple system of levers connected to the air vents. The advantages of these devices are autonomy, reliability, simplicity and high power. This system works as follows: when the temperature drops, the weight acting on the lever changes, as a result, the structure tilts in the right direction and thus opens the window. If the temperature indicators change to the previous ones, the design returns to its original position. Each lever - two containers connected by a flexible hose, filled with liquid, one of which is located indoors, the other outside. The internal container plays the role of a thermometer, it is completely tight and partially filled with air. The outer vessel is a kind of weighting agent. As the temperature inside the greenhouse rises, the laws of physics turn on: the air in the vessel heats up, expands and displaces the fluid, which flows through the flexible hose into the external container. Under the influence of its weight, the window opens. When cooling the air, the reverse process occurs.

Hydraulic systems are quite simple both in manufacturing and in installation, and are great for creating a ventilation system in a small greenhouse or greenhouse. However, there are also disadvantages. For example, it will take at least 20 minutes to cool the liquid, that is, in the event of a sharp cooling, the window will not have time to close in time, as a result, the plants may suffer.

For example, Delivery can be scheduled based on automatically controlling the growth environment and collecting data.

Multiple wireless sensors are set up within the Smart Greenhouse. Temperature, humidity, lighting intensity, and carbon dioxide levels are measured through electronic and environmental sensors and data collected are exported to an edge computer. Furthermore, this data is also stored in Cloud. Up until now, a single computer controlled each equipment and multiple environmental conditions were managed individually. Because each equipment was wired, there were limitations on its position and number. However, in a Smart Greenhouse, a single computer can control multiple equipment, minimizing the number of wiring, and all data are automatically collected to the edge computer through a wireless network. There is no need to go back and forth to the greenhouse, since each setting for the cultivating environment to watering the crops are automatically controlled based on a predetermined formula.

Since an entirely new system was implemented, we did not have enough experience during the development phase. We held many discussions to re-evaluate the meaning of added value for our customers through our products and succeeded in newly establishing our efforts. There was also the issue of the development team being experts on IoT and AI, but beginners when it came to agriculture. What kind of crops need which kind of care? This was the type of questions and challenges we managed to solve one at a time, with the cooperation from members of the Bio Innovation Center and other partner companies, who were expertise on plants and agriculture. After repeatedly making an infinite number of prototypes, a successful prototype was finally created for the Smart Greenhouse.

With the test launch of the greenhouse, we started growing tomatoes. We were able to establish our own timing of when the tomatoes became ripe and a system to collect this data. We also developed an algorithm estimating the maturity of the tomato from the several tens of thousands of images collected through the camera. Use of information technology advances with intelligence as data volume increases, allowing temperatures and humidity to be adjusted and delivery to be scheduled with high precision. It also leads to other solutions of improving precision of automatic controls and saving energy.

Pic.1- IoT Smart Greenhouse

The second group is electrical systems. The main parts are fan and relay. When a critical temperature value is reached, the relay activates and turns on the fan. Advantages of the system: high power, convenient adjustment, increased sensitivity. An electric window pane automatic for a greenhouse takes up minimal space, so it can be easily installed anywhere in the room. The action algorithm is set based on the growing conditions of the cultures; it can be elementary or quite complex.

Unfortunately, the electrical device also has disadvantages. The most important of them is a sudden power outage. If it occurs on a hot day, the entire crop may die. That is why the electric ventilation system is supplemented by a backup power source. A modern proven option is a battery-powered mechanism that recharges from solar panels.

The third group of systems is bimetallic. These systems consist of a pair of metal plates, which differ in the coefficient of thermal expansion. When heated, one plate takes the form of an arc and opens the transom, when cooled, respectively, returns it to its previous position. These are inexpensive

standalone devices that have one minus - low power. Therefore, the bimetallic device is optimal only for opening small windows.

Humidity and temperature sensors

For timely watering of plants and airing the greenhouses, the ventilation and automatic irrigation systems include temperature and humidity sensors. Humidity sensors (DV) are devices that convert the indicators of relative air humidity to certain values (usually a capacitive value). These sensors are a system of two conductors connected to a weak current source in series with a resistor, and placed in an environment whose humidity must be controlled. The more moisture in the medium's volume between the electrodes, the higher its conductivity, the lower the resistance of the medium's section (volume) between the electrodes and the stronger the current through this section, coming from the electrode to the electrode. The less moisture - the lower the conductivity of the medium (higher resistance) between the electrodes and the weaker the current through the electrodes. This is a property of the environment and is used to create sensors for soil and air humidity in greenhouses.

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